

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MacEnulty II****FIRST NAME: Earl****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied X US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did X did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord for Mac, version 15.37)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **EUCLID believes in the core value of academic integrity. Plagiarism is a violation of this foundational premise. Which of the following is NOT an incident of plagiarism?**
 - If a writer does not copy word for word what a source says, they do not have to cite it.
 - A writer does not have to cite common knowledge, i.e., wearing seat-belts saves lives or smoking cigarettes is harmful.¹**
 - If a writer quotes a source verbatim by using quotation marks, they only have to reference the source in a “Signal Phrase.”
 - If a writer puts another person’s research in their own words, they do not have to cite where they learned the information because it is theirs now.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 9.

2. **Mary Turabian is a strong proponent of which of the following regarding hypothesis and thesis creation?**
- The adroit researcher always has a clear, established hypothesis in mind before starting research.
 - The adroit researcher establishes a clear thesis and detailed outline before beginning the drafting of a paper.
 - The adroit researcher determines their research paper is successful by completing the paper with their pre-drafting hypothesis having remained unchanged and intact.
 - The adroit researcher keeps an open mind during the drafting process so that new and relevant information can inform the final thesis.²**
3. **Dealing with gender neutral language is a paradigm shift for many aspects of modern society. Which of the following is the best option for addressing changing global norms in this area?**
- Using the generic ‘he’ is still an acceptable practice depending on the higher up an established hierarchy one goes.
 - Avoid using the generic ‘he’ because in most cases one is just as likely to address a woman.
 - Using the plural form, such as ‘they/them/their’ is the most gender inclusive form of addressing gender neutral bias.³**
 - Alternating between the generic “he,” “she,” and “they” in academic writing provides equal opportunity for both genders.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Eighth edition, (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013) 48.

³ Tim Cooper et al., *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. (European Commission’s Directorate-General for Translation, EU Publication Office 2011) 47.

4. **Zotero is an app that allows for efficient documenting and citing of sources in a research paper. Which of the following is NOT a function of Zotero?**
- Zotero can import information directly into your bibliographic database from sources found on-line.
 - Zotero can import on-line information for reading off-line at a later time.
 - Zotero can insert your entire library of “works cited” and “bibliography” into your paper with one click.
 - Zotero can, based on your search history, seek and import other relevant websites and sources for use in your research.⁴**
5. **“Works Cited” and “Bibliography” are two different references in your paper. Which is the following is the best differentiation between the two.**
- A bibliography cites only information quoted in your paper while the “Works Cited” details information from sources that you quoted word for word.
 - “Works Cited” details all information cited in your paper while “Bibliography” lists all research used even if it was not cited.⁵**
 - “Works Cited” and “Bibliography” are the same thing. “Works Cited” is used in personal response papers while “Bibliography” is used for only major papers.
 - “Works Cited” and “Bibliography” are the same thing. “Works Cited” is used in major papers while “Bibliography” is used for only personal response papers.

⁴ Nathanael Warren, *How to Manage and Cite Sources using Zotero Standalone with the Google Chrome Plugin*, (YouTube Video, 10:13, April 28, 2013), <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yJiPuoGxvHo&feature=emb_logo>.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 59.

6. **The actual process of writing can be a chore at times. Which of the following is a helpful hint suggested by Mary Turabian?**
- Don't wait to "feel inspired" to write. Inspiration is like a muscle you can train to kick in for you.
 - Try to sit down and write at roughly the same time each day.**⁶
 - Never start writing until you have all your research completed and a detailed outline.
 - Choose a topic that interests you or you already know something about. If you are bored, your audience will be too.
7. **Define the Oxford Comma.**
- The Oxford Comma is the British habit of using the comma in a financial amount in place of the US style of a period (i.e., \$1,000,00).
 - The Oxford Comma is the removal of the comma directly preceding the conjunction in a list of items.
 - The Oxford Comma is the British habit of using the period in a financial amount in place of the US style of a comma (i.e., \$1,000.00).
 - The Oxford Comma is the placement of the comma directly preceding the conjunction in a list of items.**⁷
8. **When doing research, there are three definitions of sources. Which of the following is NOT one of the three broad categories of understood sources?**
- Primary sources are original works (i.e., diaries, letters or manuscripts).

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 34.

⁷ Ibid., 174.

- Secondary sources are books or articles that analyze primary sources.
 - Tertiary sources are based on secondary sources (i.e., an encyclopedia).
 - Academic sources are journals that are peer-reviewed.⁸**
9. **There are many differences between US and UK English. Which of the following is NOT a difference?**
- In US English, punctuation always goes inside the closing quotation mark.
 - In UK English, punctuation always goes outside the closing quotation mark.
 - In US English, never use a period after a title (i.e., Mr or Dr).⁹**
 - In UK English, never use a period after a title (i.e., Mr or Dr).
10. **Which of the following is NOT true regarding Thesis Statements?**
- Thesis statements are an absolute must for your paper.
 - If you do not have one, get one!
 - Your thesis statement should be early in your paper, preferably in the first paragraph.
 - These are all true regarding thesis statements.¹⁰**

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 24.

⁹ Tim Cooper, 44.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 14.

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